

Learning Efficient In-store Picking Strategies to Reduce Customer Encounters in Omnichannel Retail

Abstract

Omnichannel retailers are reinventing stores to meet the growing demand of the online channel. Several retailers now use stores as supporting distribution centers to offer quicker Buy-Online-Pickup-In-Store (BOPS) and Ship-From-Store (SFS) services. They resort to in-store picking to serve online orders using existing assets. However, in-store picking operations require picker carts traveling through store aisles, competing for store space, and possibly harming the offline customer experience. To learn picking policies that acknowledge interactions between pickers and offline customers, we formalize a new problem called Dynamic In-store Picker Routing Problem (diPRP). This problem considers a picker that tries to pick online orders (*seeking*) while minimizing customer encounters (*hiding*) – preserving the offline customer experience. We model the problem as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) and solve it using a hybrid solution approach comprising mathematical programming and reinforcement learning components. Computational experiments on synthetic instances suggest that the algorithm converges to efficient policies. We apply our solution approach in the context of a large European retailer to assess the proposed policies regarding the number of orders picked and customers encountered. The learned policies are also tested in six different retail settings, demonstrating the flexibility of the proposed approach. Our work suggests that retailers should be able to scale the in-store picking of online orders without jeopardizing the experience of offline customers. The policies learned using the proposed solution approach reduced the number of customer encounters by up to 50%, compared to policies solely focused on picking orders. Thus, to pursue omnichannel strategies that adequately trade-off operational efficiency and customer experience, retailers cannot rely on actual simplistic picking strategies, such as choosing the shortest possible route.

Keywords: omnichannel retail, in-store picking, Markov decision process, reinforcement learning, real-world application

1. Introduction

The online channel has been gaining market share year-on-year across different retail categories (Caro et al., 2020). This trend has triggered retailers to handle complex decision-making processes around managing offline and online channels. Regarding the offline channel, retail managers were called upon to re-imagine the role of physical retail stores (Adhi et al., 2022). While some believe that physical retail may be “dead”, others have many reasons to defend it as a way to differentiate from the competition, offering great experiential shopping based on good customer service (Dennis, 2018). Moreover, the physical channel remains essential for some retail categories, such as groceries (Barbee et al., 2021). For the online channel, retailers had to redesign their logistic strategies and rethink how the fulfillment process of online orders should be scaled (Calzavara et al., 2023).

To merge these two perspectives, many retailers recognize that focusing on omnichannel retailing is the way to go (Cai and Lo, 2020). This option is based on the promise that omnichannel retail may help to enrich the customer value proposition and improve operational efficiency (Gao and Su, 2017b). Despite the potential advantages of omnichannel retail, several challenges must also be faced. For example, it is not clear how to provide the online level of information (e.g., product ratings) to offline customers (Gao and Su, 2017a), select which channel most stock should be committed to (Jia et al., 2021), and decide which products should be made available in the offline and online channels (Chen et al., 2021).

An interesting example of omnichannel retailing is Buy-Online-Pickup-In-Store (BOPS). Customers find it convenient to order online and pick up the packages at a nearby retail location (Glaeser et al., 2019, Vyt et al., 2022). Research indicates that BOPS can even drain online shoppers from competitors (4.7% from the online sales and 1.8% from physical sales) (Akturk and Ketzenberg, 2022). These advantages are possibly behind the projection that BOPS is expected to grow from 44% in 2016 to 90% by 2024 in the US (Magana, 2019). Besides BOPS, retailers are offering other omnichannel fulfillment services (e.g., BOPS (Safaryan, 2022), Ship-From-Store (SFS) (Barnes, 2022), quick commerce (Nierynck, 2020)) that can reduce shipping costs and inspire impulse purchases from offline customers picking up or returning items in-store.

From a fulfillment perspective, it is clear that most retail managers are choosing to leverage their existing infrastructure (physical stores) to fulfill online orders using in-store picking (Wollenburg et al., 2018). Consequently, the activities performed at traditional warehouses on the outskirts of cities are being transferred to physical retail stores near the delivery locations. Accordingly, the number of in-house and third-party pickers inside retail stores is increasing considerably (Young, 2022), so retailers can face the growth in the number of requests that must be fulfilled in short delivery times. In this setting, we focus on supporting (grocery) retailers to effectively handle this new, complex, relevant reality of instore-picking.

From an efficiency perspective, retailers face difficulties fulfilling the growing demand for online orders with stores, as these are primarily designed for customers, not pickers (Ritter, 2020). Moreover, most physical stores do not have sufficient backroom space to settle a warehouse optimized for picking all products that can appear in online orders (Pires et al., 2021). As a result, it is essential to provide systems that can aid pickers in navigating through retail stores when they are not adequately aware of the locations of every product. From a service perspective, retailers strive to minimize the disturbance caused to in-store customers (Dethlefs et al., 2022). According to Moran (2022), “*Picking online orders is still causing headaches for grocers on multiple fronts, with (...) in-store shoppers jostling with e-commerce workers to select products in the aisles*”. Overall, there is a need, which literature has overlooked, to balance (offline) customer experience with operational efficiency (Kohan, 2023).

Research on in-store picking operations has been focusing on improving operational efficiency, ignoring the urgent need to explore new in-store picking policies that can safeguard

offline customers’ experience. To balance this efficiency-service trade-off, retailers are in dire need of innovative picking policies that can reduce the number of offline customer encounters (hiding in-store pickers), which are seen as harmful events for the perceived quality of the offline shopping experience, while guaranteeing that traditional picking efficiency standards are not erased (seeking online orders). Motivated by the real case of a European retailer that is also being pushed to perform more in-store picking, this paper focuses on the satisfaction of online orders while acknowledging the impact on offline customers’ experience. These online orders are placed on the website of the retailer; they are picked up in-store and then can be delivered at home or picked up by the customer at the store.

We aim to provide a general methodology for retailers to assess offline customer-oriented picking policies for online orders in their omnichannel context and support their decision to implement these policies in practice. This objective is aligned with the concerns of multiple retailers worldwide, which typically view the presence of in-store customers as a constraint when designing operational models for using stores to fulfill online orders. Retailers know that offline customers are the most profitable ones. Hence, online orders should be fulfilled without encumbering offline customer shopping experiences (Dayarian and Pazour, 2022, Hübner et al., 2016). Note that shopping experience quality measurements comprise several metrics (Dabholkar et al., 1995, Chou et al., 2021), but in in-store picking contexts, retailers are now majorly concerned with undesired picker encounters (Dow, 2021).

To achieve picking policies that can be adapted to the dynamic customer flows of a retail store and help to mitigate the challenges above, we introduce a new problem called Dynamic In-store Picker Routing Problem (diPRP). This sequential decision problem considers a dynamic retail store environment. It seeks to define a picking policy that maximizes the number of orders picked while minimizing the number of customer encounters. Modeling uncertain customer flows inside a store is a core element of this challenge. Traditional methods for aiding pickers based on stochastic mathematical programming will likely result in intractable Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) models and are not suited to capture the dynamics of a sequential decision problem. Therefore, the diPRP is modeled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) and solved through a well-known reinforcement learning technique. The picking policies are obtained by employing a hybrid Q-learning algorithm that maximizes immediate and future rewards (i.e., a positive reward is received when a product is picked, and a negative reward is received when an offline customer is encountered, i.e., disturbed) by providing the best actions (i.e., picker movements) to be performed by the order picker. The objective is to pick the largest number of orders (operational efficiency) while avoiding customer encounters (shopping experience).

We provide evidence on how one can profit from real-world data and orchestrate mathematical programming, simulation, and machine learning techniques to solve a relevant practical problem in omnichannel retail - the diPRP. The scientific contributions of this work are three-fold:

1. We formalize a new and relevant problem in retail where a picker picks online orders inside a retail store while avoiding physical customer encounters - the diPRP.
2. We solve the dynamic problem using a hybrid Q-learning algorithm, which includes MIP and MDP components to determine a picking policy adapted to the dynamic environment of an in-store picking operation.
3. We provide computational experiments on the algorithm convergence using synthetic instances and derive managerial insights on four different picking policies validated on a real-world application partnered with a large European retailer. Additionally, we test the learned policies in six different retail settings, demonstrating the flexibility of our method.

These insights aim at helping retailers to make better decisions related to their omnichannel strategies and ensure a solid ground to scale new fulfillment options based on existing stores.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature on in-store picker routing problems. Section 3 describes the problem setting and presents the inherent retail store simulation environment used in our study. Section 4 details the proposed solution approach based on a Q-learning algorithm. Section 5 presents the computational experiments performed on synthetic instances, which showcases the algorithm convergence. Section 6 exposes a real-world application in a European retail store and tests the learned policies in six different retail settings. Finally, Section 7 presents the main findings of this work and suggests future research directions.

2. Literature Review

Our research relates to two main research streams: in-store picking strategies and routing problems that can be adapted to the store environment. The following subsections provide an overview of the literature regarding in-store picking strategies (Section 2.1). Then, we review recent approaches dealing with picker routing problems (Section 2.2), dynamic routing problems (Section 2.3), and dynamic picker routing problems (Section 2.4). We consider that these topics cover not only the main problem setting we aim at but also the modeling and solution approach techniques needed to tackle our problem - diPRP -, which consists of picking products in a dynamic store environment, a new type of picking operation.

2.1. In-store picking strategies

The most common online order fulfillment solutions discussed in the literature are the warehouse-based and the store-based models (Fernie et al., 2010, Mkansi et al., 2011, Hübner et al., 2016). In the warehouse-based model, online orders are fulfilled from warehouses dedicated to e-commerce purchases. In the store-based model, orders are fulfilled by the existing retail stores. Currently, when picking online orders, in-store picking (store-based) strategies are the most common (Mangiaracina et al., 2018).

Indeed, in-store picking strategies present some advantages that can justify their rapid adoption. First, since they rely on existing assets, they do not require substantial investments in new facilities. Second, large store networks with a wide geographical presence decrease the average distance and delivery cost, allowing retailers to offer a better service (Hübner et al., 2016). Third, services like BOPS and SFS can be offered without requiring an additional network flow (warehouse to store) that would increase the supply chain complexity.

Nonetheless, in-store picking activities also pose additional challenges. First, this order fulfillment strategy is limited by a lower capacity constraint (compared to warehouse-based strategies). This means this strategy is not as scalable and may only be suitable for limited demand contexts (Fernie et al., 2010). Second, as physical customers and pickers co-exist in the same space, they will compete for the same stock, increasing the stock-out risk and slowing down the order preparation rate due to congestion events (Calzavara et al., 2023). Third, the layout of traditional stores is designed to showcase products, not to allow for efficient picking (Hübner et al., 2016).

Few recent studies have been proposed to overcome the disadvantages above and evaluate the efficiency of in-store picking strategies at several levels. Pietri et al. (2021) propose new optimization strategies for in-store picking, improving picking and packing time efficiency. The authors state that the literature does not provide any approach to optimize in-store order picking in a BOPS system. Difrancesco et al. (2021) model the in-store fulfillment process of an

omnichannel retailer using SFS strategy to fulfill online orders in a dense urban market. One of the decisions included in the model is the time between two consecutive cut-off times to start the in-store picking process. Delays can benefit picking efficiency but induce higher stock-out risk and late deliveries. [Calzavara et al. \(2023\)](#) propose a cost function based on logistics costs to compare four strategies to respond to e-grocery shopping. The authors consider serving orders directly from stores (in-store); using dedicated stores closed to customers (dark stores); performing integrated fulfillment of online orders from a dedicated hub and from the stores (single e-hub); and using dedicated online distribution centers to deliver directly to customers (multi e-hub). The number of customers and the size of the orders are critical characteristics of the tested settings.

Among the different fulfillment strategies, which can leverage in-store picking, BOPS has received the most attention. However, most papers do not distinguish between BOPS with and without in-store picking. Most works focus on comparing the cost of fulfillment options or evaluating the utility of BOPS operations ([Lin et al., 2021](#), [Akturk and Ketzenberg, 2022](#)). Complementarily, several papers explore BOPS from other perspectives (e.g., marketing, omnichannel promotions, customer product choices, pricing strategies, and service quality). Still, the literature on optimizing in-store logistics operations is scarce ([Chou et al., 2021](#)).

This paper aims to fill this gap and show how in-store picking can shape itself to co-live with a strategy oriented to improve the offline customer shopping experience. We focus on the particular case of a retailer with an extensive store network without picking operations in the backroom, serving limited online demand. We fill a gap in the existing literature, as our analysis will focus on the trade-off between operational efficiency against customer experience-related metrics.

2.2. Picker routing problems

The picker or order routing problem was introduced by [Ratliff and Rosenthal \(1983\)](#) and is typically modeled as a Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) on a Steiner graph ([Letchford et al., 2013](#), [Cambazard and Catusse, 2018](#), [Rodríguez-Pereira et al., 2019](#)). Several problem extensions have been proposed in the literature to adapt the standard model to real-world cases with specific business constraints ([Chabot et al., 2017](#), [Quader and Castillo-Villar, 2018](#), [Ardjmand et al., 2018](#)) and to combine subsequent problems, such as storage and batching ([van Gils et al., 2018](#)). In terms of solution methods, this problem is usually tackled with heuristics ([Theys et al., 2010](#)), but essential problem properties were discovered to increase the efficiency of exact methods based on mathematical formulations ([Cornuéjols et al., 1985](#), [Pansart et al., 2018](#)). Recently, new formulations have been proposed to increase the size of the instances solved exactly ([Scholz et al., 2016](#)) and to integrate the order picking problem with other activities in the supply chain ([Roodbergen et al., 2015](#)), as this remains to be a relevant problem in warehouse operations management. Picker routing problems are typically solved within narrow aisle warehouses ([Roodbergen and de Koster, 2001](#), [Roodbergen and Koster, 2001](#), [de Koster et al., 2007](#), [Chabot et al., 2018](#), [Masae et al., 2020](#)) and not inside stores. Considering layouts that are not optimized for picking operations and can be crowded with customers leads to a new context that has never been studied in the order-picking literature. In a store, product layouts may be very irregular, and most graph properties assumed in order-picking literature are not applicable. Furthermore, customer shopping paths can be chaotic and are not known *a priori*, meaning that picking problems are *more* stochastic and dynamic.

2.3. Dynamic routing problems

Although stochastic dynamic routing has a 30-year history, most papers published in this field are recent. Over half of the articles in the literature review of [Ulmer et al. \(2020\)](#) have been

published after 2010. Other literature reviews on this topic have been published by [Berbeglia et al. \(2010\)](#), [Pillac et al. \(2013\)](#), [Ritzinger et al. \(2016\)](#), [Psaraftis et al. \(2016\)](#), and [Ojeda Rios et al. \(2021\)](#). It is worth mentioning that multiple trends (e.g., e-commerce growth, sharing economies, and sustainability) and technological advances (e.g., digital connectivity, big data, and automation) are fostering the development of new approaches to tackle dynamic routing problems ([Savelsbergh and Van Woensel, 2016](#)). To solve these problems, the unified framework for stochastic programming proposed by [Powell \(2019\)](#) has been determinant, as researchers have been adapting it to tackle dynamic problems modeled as MDPs. To turn dynamic programming applicable to large real-world problems, the approximate dynamic programming approaches presented in [Powell \(2007\)](#) have also been an influential reference in this field.

More recently, several attempts have also been tried to solve routing problems modeled as MDPs through Reinforcement Learning techniques ([Nazari et al. \(2018\)](#), [Li et al. \(2021\)](#), [Kullman et al. \(2022\)](#)). However, despite their potential to be used in new contexts, these methods are still felt unexplored by the routing community, as suggested by [Hildebrandt et al. \(2021\)](#).

2.4. Dynamic picker routing problem

In some business contexts, it is interesting to consider a dynamic variant of the picker routing problem. These problems arise when new information allows for better planning or execution of the picking operations (i.e., a new order arrived). Concerning dynamic picker routing problems, the literature is very scarce. [Gong and Koster \(2008\)](#) consider picking operations where picking information can dynamically change in a picking cycle. Based on a stochastic polling theory approach, the authors suggest that shorter order throughput times and higher on-time service completion ratios can be achieved. [Lu et al. \(2016\)](#) consider dynamic order-picking strategies that allow changes in the picking lists during a picking route. The authors allow for re-optimizing the optimal route during the picking operation and achieve better solution quality when compared to the static version of the problem.

These authors consider that dynamic information arriving is only related to customer arrivals. However, in a store, two types of entities can perform picking: offline customers and online order pickers. Pickers can gather information on the customers' locations as they perform their picking paths. This maps into a new dynamic picking routing problem. However, the interactions between in-store pickers and offline customers have not been considered yet. In other words, no approach has been proposed for solving the dynamic in-store picker routing problem.

Despite the many articles dealing with picker routing problems, no publication has considered the new environment in-store picking teams face. Indeed, the pandemic context of 2020 brought new operations to be managed and new challenges to be tackled while pursuing different objectives. For instance, constraints imposed on the number of customers inside of a store may turn retailers interested in guiding customers through their shopping paths to accelerate customers' shopping process, as opposed to making them stay for longer inside the store ([Hui et al., 2013](#), [Boros et al., 2015](#), [Hirpara and Parikh, 2021](#)). Each customer in-store is also solving its picker routing problem to define its shopping path. The fact that customers do not know the exact position of the products and that some customers may have picking-sequence preferences ([Larson et al., 2005](#)) can induce chaotic flows of customers through the aisles of a store ([Chen et al., 2015](#), [Li et al., 2017](#)). This means that the store state is not known *a priori* when the picking route of each order picker is being defined (it is stochastic). Therefore, if we are interested in picking paths that do not disturb customers' shopping experience, current approaches to the picker routing problem cannot tackle this issue. This is a gap that we address in this work.

3. Problem description

In this section, we formalize the diPRP by describing all the relevant elements included in the considered retail store environment, the picker agents that will make decisions inside the store, and the MDP that is proposed to model the associated dynamic problem. We should note that we consider an omnichannel retail setting with limited online demand and possibly served using in-store picking. Additionally, we assume that pickers are not slowed down in crowded aisles and that there is enough stock on the shelves, ignoring the necessity for shelf replenishment.

Hence, Section 3.1 details the retail store environment, including the store graph, the models for simulating the shopping paths of physical customers, and the online order arrivals composed of a set of picking positions. Section 3.2 clarifies the behavior of an order picker and the information available in each step (e.g., following product to be picked and physical customers nearby). Section 3.3 describes the MDP that models the dynamic problem we aim to solve, including decision epochs, states, actions, transition function, rewards, and objective function.

3.1. Retail Store Environment

To model a realistic retail store environment, we resort to a simulation environment considering physical customer arrivals and online order arrivals. The store is modeled as a sparse graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ where the set of vertices (locations in-store) is partitioned into vertex 0, which is the entrance of the store where the shopping paths start, vertices $\{1, \dots, v\}$, corresponding to v positions inside the store, and vertex $v + 1$, which is the position where the shopping paths end (i.e., a cashier or an order preparation zone). Physical customers arrive at the store following a Poisson distribution with a mean value of λ^{Store} customers per time period. Each physical customer $c \in \mathcal{C}$ moves through the aisles of the store, navigating through the graph \mathcal{G} at speed $speed^{Customer}$ and according to a given shopping path θ_c containing a sequence of locations in-store. A physical customer takes $service_time^{Customer}$ time periods to pick a product located at a particular node. The maximum number of customers inside the store can never surpass the capacity of the store $|\mathcal{C}|$, and the maximum number of customers in the same store node is m . The arrival rate of online orders is also a random variable, which follows a Poisson distribution with a mean value of λ^{Online} orders per time period. Each online order $o \in \mathcal{O}$ is composed of a set of picking positions $\mathcal{L}_o \subset \mathcal{V}$ that need to be visited to pick the ordered products. Figure 1 presents a schematic representation of the considered omnichannel retail setting.

3.2. Picker agents

Whenever an online order o arrives, it must be allocated to an idle picker. At that moment, a picking sequence θ_o is defined according to a business decision rule (e.g., shortest route, heavy items first, and frozen products at the end). In this work, we assume that these picking sequences minimize the traveled distance, i.e., the shortest route, - maximizing operational efficiency, which is the typical case in practice. The picker follows a given picking sequence, yet he is interested in avoiding customer encounters not to disturb their shopping experience. Therefore, between every pair of products to be picked, the picker solves a shortest path problem while avoiding customers currently in the store. The dynamic component of this problem corresponds to solving a series of dynamic shortest path problems. The fundamental trade-off that is inherent to this problem comes from the fact that the order picker follows a predefined sequence of picking positions that are provided by a decision rule adopted by the retail store (e.g., shortest routes), but he/she needs to avoid customer encounters in the path between two picking positions. The position of the customers in-store is not known in advance, and it is only revealed when the picker looks through the aisle. Each picker receives several online orders throughout the day and, consequently, multiple picking sequences to execute.

Figure 1: The retail store environment considers a picker that picks online orders, both from BOPS and SFS, while the physical customers perform their shopping paths.

3.3. Dynamic picker routing problem as a Markov decision process

To formulate the diPRP as finite horizon MDP with T time periods, consider a decision epoch $k \in 0, 1, \dots, T$ at which a decision for the next position node to visit inside the store should be made. A new decision epoch k is triggered whenever the picker arrives at a new position. Each decision epoch k is associated with a decision state s_k . At the initial state s_0 and initial decision epoch $k = 0$, the picker is located at the starting depot node 0. At the terminal decision epoch $k = T$, the picker returns to the finishing depot node $v + 1$ after picking the order that is currently being picked. At a state s_k , the system receives updated information on the number of customers at the same position of the picker and adjacent positions (connected by an arc). Based on the system information about current online orders, an action a_k (i.e., the next position to visit targeting a product or the depot) needs to be decided. Each position that is visited increases the total travel time and, potentially, the number of customer encounters. The goal of the picker is to find optimal paths, short and quick to traverse, while minimizing the number of customer encounters. The picker is positively rewarded for each product picked. Overall, the problem faced by the in-store picker can be modeled as a MDP composed of four components, namely, (1) a set of states \mathcal{S} ; (2) a set of actions \mathcal{A} ; (3) a reward function R ; and the transition probabilities P .

Decision epochs A decision epoch k begins when a picker arrives at a new location in-store.

States The state of the system at decision epoch k is defined by the tuple $s_k = (n_k, z_k, t_k)$, where $n_k \in \mathcal{V}$ is the picker's current location, $z_k = (z_k(1), z_k(2), \dots, z_k(|\mathcal{L}_o|))$ is a vector contain-

ing the status of each picking location of an online order o at decision epoch k , and $t_k \in [0, T]$ is the arrival time at location n_k . For each picking location of an online order, $z_k(\cdot)$ takes on a value in the set $\{0, 1\}$:

$$z_k(\cdot) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if picking location has not been visited by time } t_k \\ 1, & \text{if picking location has been visited by time } t_k \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In the initial state $s_0 = (0, z_0, 0)$, the picker is located at the order preparation zone and $z_0(n)$ is 0 or 1 for each picking location $n \in \mathcal{V} \setminus \{0\}$. The final decision epoch is attained when the picker reaches the terminal state s_K in the set $\{(0, z_k, t_k) : t_k \in [0, T], z_k \in \{0, 1\}^{|\mathcal{L}^o|}\}$, where the picker has returned to the preparation zone by time T and the status of the picking locations of the online order being served is 0 or 1. The state space is the set $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{V} \times [0, T] \times \{0, 1\}^{|\mathcal{L}^o|}$.

Actions An action at decision epoch k is an assignment of the picker to an in-store location belonging to \mathcal{V} . When the picker is at state s_k , the set of feasible actions corresponding to the possible arcs leaving n_k is given by

$$\mathcal{A}(s_k) = \{a_k \in \{n \in \mathcal{V} : (s_k, n) \in \mathcal{E}\} : \quad (2)$$

Transitions Following the selection of action a_k from state s_k , the process transitions to a new state s_{k+1} in decision epoch $k + 1$. There is no uncertainty regarding the position in which the picker will be in the next decision epoch. However, the unknown information regarding the number of customers encountered is revealed. This information is a realization of Ω_{k+1} and is given by ω_{k+1} . Let $\widehat{R}_{k+1}(s_k, a_k, \omega_{k+1})$ be the random negative reward accrued at decision epoch k when selecting action a_k from state s_k and observing random information ω_{k+1} .

Rewards When the picker occupies state s_k and performs an action $a_k \in \mathcal{A}$, a reward is accrued depending on the conditions of the in-store location to which the picker moves. The reward is composed of four components, (1) a fixed negative reward for each picker step, (2) the number of in-store customers in the same location of the picker, (3) the number of in-store customers in the locations reachable from the picker location, and (4) a positive reward for a picked product. The number of steps given from the last decision epoch is given by ϕ_1 , the number of customers in the same location is given by ϕ_2 , the number of customers nearby is given by ϕ_3 , and the number products picked is given by ϕ_4 . These four components can be adjusted using weights w_1 to w_4 , respectively. The reward $r_k(s_k, a_k, \omega_{k+1})$, which is a stochastic variable depending on the store environment, is defined as

$$r_k(s_k, a_k, \omega_{k+1}) = -w_1 \phi_1(\omega_{k+1}) - w_2 \phi_2(\omega_{k+1}) - w_3 \phi_3(\omega_{k+1}) + w_4 \phi_4(\omega_{k+1}) \quad (3)$$

Objective The objective is to maximize the expected sum of rewards across decision epochs, that is, if weights are properly set, trying to pick as many orders as possible while minimizing in-store customer encounters. Let π be a sequence of actions a_0, a_1, \dots, a_T for every decision epoch $k = 0, \dots, T$. The aim is to find an optimal policy π to maximize the total expected reward. The objective function, conditional on initial state s_0 , is the following

$$\min_{\pi} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^T r_k | s_0 \right] \quad (4)$$

4. Solution approach

The diPRP defined in Section 3 demands solution techniques with different scopes and purposes: (1) whenever an online order arrives, a Shopping Routing Problem (SRP) model, an MIP, needs to be solved to obtain a picking sequence according to predefined decision rules; and (2) for each picking sequence and every pair of products on that sequence, a sequential decision problem is solved and recursively updates the policy via a Q-learning algorithm. Figure 2 presents an overview of the devised approach, showing where each technique is needed and how the picker agent interacts with the store environment.

In Section 4.1, we describe the problem, the mathematical formulation, and the solution approach used to obtain the picking sequences to feed the picker agent-related procedures. In Section 4.2, we describe the proposed Q-learning approach to learn an optimal policy for efficiently picking orders while avoiding in-store customer encounters. Section 4.3 provides an example of picking paths obtained with different policies and an example of what a policy obtained with Q-Learning looks like.

Figure 2: Approach overview including a detailed breakdown of the picker agent.

4.1. SRP definition

To introduce the standard SRP, consider the retail store environment described in Section 3.1. Each edge $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$ is a pair of positions associated with a sequence of grid steps corresponding to the shortest path between picking position i and j . Edges are weighted by a factor w_{ij} , typically representing the arc's distance or duration. Again, let $\mathcal{L}_o \subset \mathcal{V}$ be a subset of vertices corresponding to the picking positions that have to be visited to pick a given shopping list o . The main objective of the picker is to pick all the products in the shopping list while minimizing the distance (or duration) of its shopping path.

4.1.1. SRP Mathematical formulation

To model the SRP, we use binary decision variables x_{ij} for defining routing decisions. Let x_{ij} be the binary variables indicating whether an edge (i, j) is traversed. The proposed formulation reads as follows:

SRP:

$$\text{minimize } \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}} w_{ij} x_{ij} \quad (5)$$

s.t.

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} x_{ji} = 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{L}_o \cup \{0\} \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} x_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{L}_o \cup \{v+1\} \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{O}} x_{ij} \leq |\mathcal{O}| - 1 \quad \forall \mathcal{O} \subset \mathcal{V}, i \neq j \quad (8)$$

$$x \in \{0, 1\}. \quad (9)$$

Objective function (5) minimizes the total distance (or duration) of the shopping path. The flow conservation at the starting position, product picking positions, and finishing position are ensured by constraints (6) and (7). Constraints (8) are added to eliminate sub-tours. Finally, constraints (9) define the type and bounds of each variable.

4.1.2. SRP Solution approach

In the context of diPRPs, each SRP needs to be solved in fractions of a second. Furthermore, in a simulation procedure (later used for optimizing the picking policies), we need to solve hundreds if not thousands of SRP instances. Relying solely on a mathematical solver is not sufficient when the picking lists comprise a considerably large number of products. Therefore, we tackle this problem with an efficient exact solution approach that can quickly solve the mathematical formulation presented in the previous section. We employ a cutting planes algorithm where cuts are added to remove fractional solutions from the admissible region of the linear relaxation (Algorithm 1).

Algorithm 1 Cutting Planes

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1: procedure CUTTINGPLANES( $\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{L}_o$ )
2:    $CutsAdded \leftarrow True; X \leftarrow \emptyset; Y \leftarrow \emptyset; Z \leftarrow 0;$ 
3:   while  $CutsAdded$  do
4:      $X \leftarrow$  Solve assignment model (5)-(7) considering sets  $\mathcal{V}$  and  $\mathcal{L}_o$ ;
5:      $Y \leftarrow$  Separate arcs in sets of connected components;
6:      $Z \leftarrow$  Count the number of connected component sets in  $Y$ ;
7:     if  $Z = 1$  then
8:        $CutsAdded \leftarrow False;$ 
9:     else
10:      Add cuts (8) to eliminate sub-tours;
11:       $CutsAdded \leftarrow True;$ 
12:     if  $CutsAdded$  then
13:        $X \leftarrow$  Convert positive variables to integer;
14:     else
15:       if All edges in the solution are integer then
16:          $\theta_o \leftarrow$  The picking sequence is obtained from the model solution  $X$ ;
17:         return  $\theta_o$ .
```

The algorithm starts by solving a relaxed assignment model (Algorithm 1, line 4) and separating connected component sets (Algorithm 1, line 5). Suppose there is more than one

connected component set. In that case, the solution has sub-tours (Algorithm 1, line 10), and cuts are added to eliminate these sub-tours (Algorithm 1, line 11). When cuts are added, the edge variables with a positive value are converted to an integer. This process is repeated until no cuts are added after solving the relaxed assignment model, and all the edge variables are integer, meaning that the optimal solution is found (Algorithm 1, line 17).

4.2. Q-Learning

The cutting plane approach presented in Section 4.1.2 provides a sequence θ_o for picking the list of products of online order o . However, an in-store picker has multiple options to go from one picking position to another. In the SRP formulation, we assume shortest paths, that is, the steps to perform when traversing an arc (i, j) are the ones leading to the shortest distance between i and j (again, note that other decision rules can be used). Therefore, in order not to disturb in-store customers, it may be beneficial to perform different steps or detours while traveling from i to j , depending on the unknown patterns related to the movement of the customers in-store.

To obtain a routing policy that follows a given picking sequence but tries to avoid customers, we devise a Q-Learning (Watkins, 1989) approach to solve the MDP previously presented in Section 3.3. This technique belongs to reinforcement learning, a branch of approximate dynamic programming. It is a value-based method that searches for action-value functions $Q(s_k, a)$ representing the future expected reward of taking action a from state s_k .

Let us denote $V_\pi(s_k)$ as the value function that gives the total expected reward if we start from a state s_k and follow policy π . This value includes the immediate reward received at decision epoch $k + 1$ and the expected rewards to obtain in the future until the final decision epoch T . Our objective is to find the action array that maximizes the total reward obtained through the entire process. Considering the Bellman Equation (Powell, 2007), $V^*(s_k) = \max_{a_k \in \mathcal{A}(s_k)} \{r_{k+1} + \mathbb{E}[V(s_{k+1})|s_k, a]\}$, an optimal action a_k is implemented by solving the following expression,

$$a_k = \arg \max_{a_k \in \mathcal{A}(s_k)} \{r_{k+1} + \mathbb{E}[V(s_{k+1})|s_k, a]\} \quad (10)$$

In the problem we are considering, agents do not control the characteristics of the state they will end up in due to the uncertain customer shopping paths. Therefore, they only have limited influence in the next state that they will visit, depending on their current state s_k and a performed action a_k . Let $Q_\pi(s_k, a_k)$ be a function (Q-function) representing the quality of action a_k when the agent is at a given state s_k and follows policy π . We can define the optimal Q-function as $Q^*(s_k, a_k)$. The relation between $V^*(s_k)$ and $Q^*(s_k, a_k)$ is given by the following expression,

$$V^*(s_k) = \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}(s_k)} Q^*(s_k, a) \quad (11)$$

Therefore, an optimal policy π^* for the problem we aim to solve can be derived through the following expression,

$$\pi^*(s_k) = \arg \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}(s_k)} Q^*(s_k, a) \quad (12)$$

If we can identify Q^* , we have an optimal policy to control the actions of the picker agent in the store environment in which he was trained. This policy can be determined using the referred Q-Learning approach, using the Bellman equation to approximate Q^* . The Bellman equation based on a Q-function can be expressed recursively by

$$Q(s, a) = R + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s', a') \quad (13)$$

The Q-learning equation to iteratively approximate Q^* is given by

$$Q^{new}(s, a) = Q(s, a) + \alpha \left(R + \gamma \max_a Q(s', a) - Q(s, a) \right) \quad (14)$$

Where the learning rate α adjusts how different previous and new Q values are from each other. As the agent increasingly explores the environment, the approximated Q^{new} values will converge to Q^* . To extract an optimal picking policy for a store environment, we propose Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Q-Learning procedure

```

1: procedure QLEARNING( $MDP, \alpha, \gamma, \epsilon$ )
2:   Initialize  $Q(s, a)$  using random optimistic values;
3:   for each episode do
4:     Initialize the environment with the initial state  $s_0$  (picker at the depot);
5:     while  $s_k$  is not the final state (the store is not closed) do
6:       Choose an action  $a_k$  available from the current state  $s_k$  following an  $\epsilon$ -greedy strategy;
7:       Execute action  $a_k$ , receive a reward  $r_k$ , and observe a new state  $s_{k+1}$ ;
8:       Update Q-function by doing  $Q(s_k, a_k) \leftarrow Q(s_k, a_k) + \alpha \left( r_k + \gamma \arg \max_a Q(s_{k+1}, a) - Q(s_k, a_k) \right)$ 
9:     if  $Q$  converges then
10:      Break;
11:   return  $Q$ 

```

The algorithm starts by initializing the Q-function with random optimistic values (Algorithm 2, line 2). These optimistic values promote the exploration of new states. Then, a cyclic procedure is repeated for a certain number of episodes (Algorithm 2, line 3). First, the store environment initializes at the initial state s_0 (Algorithm 2, line 4) and, while it does not reach the final state s_T (Algorithm 2, line 5), it chooses an action, executes it, and updates the Q-function (Algorithm 2, lines 6 to 8). The choice of the action is performed using an ϵ -greedy, meaning that a random action is chosen with probability ϵ , and the action with the best Q value is chosen with probability $1 - \epsilon$. After finishing an episode, the algorithm verifies if the Q-function converged (i.e., checks if the maximum difference between old and new q-values is lower than a convergence threshold). If it did converge, the algorithm returns the Q-function. Otherwise, it continues to the next episode.

4.3. Illustrative example

The solution approach developed in this work converges to optimal policies substantially different from a shortest path-based policy, depending on the assumed reward shape. Figure 3 compares two paths with similar origin and destination locations. In this figure, the size of the nodes measures the average number of customers present at each location. We observe that the central aisle and the product positions in the top middle aisles were more crowded during the simulated episode. The **SP** policy (shortest path-based), in red, results in a shorter distance, but it encounters more customers. On the other hand, the **QL** policy (Q-Learning-based), in blue, results in a significant detour that, on average, encounters fewer customers.

The blue path is obtained by following a policy extracted from the Q values. Figure 4 presents an example of three steps performed using a Q-table (lookup table). Each row represents a state that is a tuple containing the current position (node 85) and the target position (node 123). Each column corresponds to a possible action considering the current positions of the picker. For instance, in the first step, the picker could walk to node 77 or node 93. Since the Q value of node 77 is larger, the picker moves to position 77.

Figure 3: Illustrative example of a **SP** (red) and a **QL** path (blue).

		Available Actions			
		A1	A2	A3	...
States	S1 (85, 123)	1 st step Q((85, 123), 77)	Q((85, 123), 93)	-	...
	S2 (77, 123)	2 nd step Q((77, 123), 62)	Q((77, 123), 85)	-	...
	S3 (62, 123)	3 rd step Q((62, 123), 54)	Q((62, 123), 63)	Q((62, 123), 77)	...
	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

Figure 4: An example with three steps obtained from the Q-table used to obtain the Q-learning path in the illustrative example.

5. Algorithm convergence

In this section, we present the computational experiments to explore the efficacy and efficiency of the proposed approach on synthetic instances. Firstly, we describe the process used to generate the synthetic instance set. Secondly, we perform a search on the training parameters to find good combinations of learning rate, discount rate, and ϵ -greediness and validate the convergence of the proposed approach on different problem sizes.

5.1. Synthetic instances

Synthetic instances were generated to validate the proposed approach by considering different simulation parameter combinations. We tested combinations of four store layouts with different sizes and three different customer concentrations inside the store. As such, store environments can be tiny, small, medium, and large, and the products of customers' shopping lists can be more concentrated near the entrance, the middle, or the back of the store. The number of products in customers' shopping lists follows a uniform distribution with a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 10 products. These products and their picking sequence are randomly chosen, and customers follow the shortest path when moving from one product position to another product position. The arrival rate of physical customers is set to 2, and the arrival rate of online orders is set to 0.2. In each episode, the store is open for 8 hours, and the maximum number of customers inside the store $|\mathcal{C}|$ is set to 50. The maximum number of customers per node m is 5, and each customer takes 30 seconds to pick a product. The walking speed is set to 1 m/s. Table 1 summarizes the sets of parameters that were used to build 12 synthetic instances. Regarding

rewards and penalties in the synthetic instances, when a picker is in the same node where a customer is, it is penalized by 3 points. If a picker is seen by a customer (i.e., the customer is in the nodes accessible by the picker), the picker is penalized by 1 point. Picker steps are penalized by 1 point, and products picked are rewarded with 100 points.

Table 1: Sets of parameters used to build the generated instances.

Store layout	{Tiny, Small, Medium, Large}
Customer concentration	{Entrance, Middle, Back}
Physical customer arrival rate	{2}
Online order arrival rate	{0.2}
Open time (h)	{8}
Maximum number of customers inside	{50}
Maximum number of customers in a location	{5}
Product picking time (s)	{30}
Walking speed (m/s)	{1}
Customer encounter penalty (p1)	{3}
Customer visible penalty (p2)	{1}
Step penalty (p3)	{1}
Picking reward (p4)	{100}

5.2. Q-learning training and results

Despite the potential of reinforcement learning approaches, tuning them is often non-trivial and time-consuming. This is essentially because testing parameter combinations can be an expensive and noisy process. To overcome these difficulties, we tested several parameter configurations to determine policies for each synthetic instance. Each configuration was run for 5000 episodes using a single thread. All computations were run on Intel Xeon @ 2.5 GHz processing units, and the mathematical solver adopted to compute picking sequences of the pickers was Gurobi 9.5. Table 2 presents the parameter sets used to build each training configuration.

Table 2: Sets of reinforcement learning parameters used to build training configurations.

Learning rate (α)	{0.95, 0.97, 0.99}
Discount rate (γ)	{0.50, 0.70, 0.90}
ϵ -greediness (ϵ)	{0.01}

The cumulative rewards obtained for the training episodes are presented in Table 3. The first two columns, “Layout” and “Paths”, indicate the layout of the store and the type of shopping paths performed by the customers. The third column, “Best Parameters”, indicates the combination of parameters ($\alpha|\gamma|\epsilon$) that obtained the values presented in the respective row. Columns four to six present the minimum, average, and maximum cumulative rewards obtained across all the tested parameter configurations. The last column shows the coefficient of variation over the last 50 observations.

We observe that the difference between the minimum and maximum cumulative rewards increases for the larger store layouts. As the problem size increases, the importance of choosing a good combination of parameters also increases. As expected, the cumulative reward obtained in larger stores is smaller, as the picker spends more time traveling through a larger number of nodes, particularly when he/she needs to return to the preparation zone. Moreover, we observe that for the last 50 observations, the coefficient of variation of the rewards is low for all instance sizes, enforcing the idea that the algorithm converged in all of them. At this point, to better understand the algorithm convergence, we present Figure 5.

Table 3: Cumulative rewards obtained in the training procedure (5000 episodes).

Layout	Paths	Best Parameters ($\alpha \gamma \epsilon$)	Cumulative rewards			
			Min.	Avg.	Max.	CV (last 50 obs.)
tiny	far	0.97 0.9 0.01	28989.54	29262.92	29440.60	0.11
tiny	middle	0.99 0.7 0.01	27240.37	28563.90	29262.10	0.11
tiny	near	0.95 0.9 0.01	28325.40	28810.05	29073.35	0.10
small	far	0.97 0.9 0.01	23471.06	26828.68	28569.88	0.11
small	middle	0.97 0.9 0.01	8571.05	21363.16	28362.71	0.10
small	near	0.97 0.9 0.01	11729.02	22830.18	28236.43	0.10
medium	far	0.99 0.9 0.01	-249624.48	-74201.81	26741.11	0.11
medium	middle	0.99 0.9 0.01	-280708.50	-136167.61	26352.44	0.12
medium	near	0.97 0.9 0.01	-275092.86	-144711.93	25733.31	0.08
large	far	0.95 0.9 0.01	-282733.08	-172079.58	22584.38	0.10
large	middle	0.95 0.9 0.01	-286259.32	-152702.76	17371.42	0.18
large	near	0.97 0.9 0.01	-285686.24	-180264.63	21524.09	0.13

Figure 5: Cumulative rewards obtained by the best parameter configurations used in synthetic instances (first 500 episodes of the training session).

The cumulative rewards suggest that the algorithms converge in a few episodes. As expected, the size of the store considered in each instance is connected to the time it takes for the cumulative rewards to converge. While in instances with a medium layout, we observe the algorithm converging after a few episodes, in instances with a large layout, the cumulative rewards stabilize after more than 200 episodes. Nonetheless, the proposed approach successfully achieves picking policies that do not demand substantial computational power.

6. Real-world application

This section details a real application in the context of a large European retailer. The devised approach was applied using the layout of a real-world store considering real shopping paths collected from customers using a mobile app that allows them to keep track of products they pick in-store as they are shopping.

An essential aspect of the devised approach is that it does not require substantial computational power. The output of the Q-learning approach is a policy in the form of a Q-table (lookup table) that can be used in simple mobile devices (i.e., phones and PDAs). Moreover, this can be improved over time in an offline or an online fashion, using new data collected from customer and picker shopping paths to update Q-tables. It is even possible to compute Q-tables

tailored for different parts of the day or week suited to the customer flows that are more likely to occur during these periods.

6.1. Real-world instance

The first step to applying the devised approach to the considered real context was to represent the retail store with substantial detail. This is a particularly challenging process due to the lack of data regarding product positions in practice. Large retailers are now digitizing physical stores as the opportunities provided by the new data collected are remarkable. However, this process is still in its infancy in the retailer considered in this study. In the retail business, several products are likely to be relocated daily for many reasons (i.e., promotional activities, new products introduced in the assortment), which increases the difficulties of maintaining reliable information on product positions. Nonetheless, we mapped products to aisles, realistically representing the real store. Figure 6 presents the store layout and graph considered in the real-world application.

Figure 6: Representation of the store layout and graph considered in the real-world application.

In this figure, the nodes represented in red are aisle intersections, and the nodes represented in blue are product positions. We opted for considering at most two product nodes inside each aisle as it already provides a good indication of the position of each product. In the considered graph, customers are allowed to enter the store by the node represented in green. After traversing their shopping path, they randomly choose one of the exit nodes represented in orange. The sequence of products picked by the physical customers is based on real-world data collected using the mobile app provided by the retailer. To compute the shortest path between each pair of products in the customer shopping path, we resorted to an implementation of a Dijkstra algorithm. The remaining parameters were set according to discussions with the retail store managers. The arrival rate of physical customers λ^{Store} is set to 10, and the arrival rate of online orders λ^{Online} is set to 0.2. The maximum number of customers allowed in the store is set to 300, and we did not set a maximum number of customers per node in the real application. Each customer takes 30 seconds to pick a product and walks at 1 m/s. The store is open for 8 hours. The picker agent is awarded 50 points for each product picked; it is penalized by 3 points for each customer encountered in the same node and is penalized by 1 for each customer seen in adjacent nodes.

To further describe the real-world store simulation environment that was used to train the picker agents, we present Figure 7 containing the distribution of the customer shopping times, a representation of the most crowded areas inside the store (average number of customers per decision epoch), and examples of category paths performed by customers picking only three products (for better visualization) and starting from the categories hygiene, beauty, and dairy.

Figure 7: Real-world store simulation environment metrics.

We observe that most customers stay in-store for 5 to 15 minutes. The most crowded nodes are the ones on the left side of the image, mostly corresponding to food products, and at the bottom of the image, corresponding to the front aisle of the store near the cashiers. The order preparation zone from which the pickers depart is located at the top right of the picture. This area is usually less crowded as it includes work tools and various materials for DIY activities. We also observe that customers follow very distinct shopping paths even if they share a few nodes/products in their shopping lists.

6.2. Training in a real-world context

The training process used in the real-world case was similar to the one presented in Section 5.2. First, we set up several training sessions considering different combinations of reinforcement learning parameters, namely, learning rates α , discount rates γ , and exploration probabilities ϵ . The reinforcement learning parameter sets used are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Sets of reinforcement learning parameters to build training configurations for the real-world instances.

Learning rate (α)	{0.1, 0.5, 0.9, 0.95, 0.97, 0.99}
Discount rate (γ)	{0.1, 0.5, 0.9, 0.95, 0.97, 0.99}
ϵ -greediness (ϵ)	{0.01, 0.03, 0.05, 0.07, 0.09}

A total of 30000 episodes were run for each configuration. Policies and the average cumulative rewards were saved every 1000 episodes. The 10 best policies (regarding average rewards) obtained in the training results related to the real retail store environment are presented in Figure 8. Every 1000 episodes, we restarted the computation of the average cumulative rewards. Note that after the first 1000 episodes, some policies were already performing better but

Figure 8: Average cumulative rewards for the top 10 policies among all parameter configurations in the real-world store environment.

had not converged. Generally, the best policies converged after 20000 episodes in the training procedure. A few policies could not match the performance of the best policies even after 30000 episodes.

In some reinforcement learning problems, average cumulative rewards obtained during the training phase (considering random actions) can differ from those obtained during the testing phase (constantly choosing the optimal action according to the Q-table). There is a large debate on how to evaluate these approaches and whether the ϵ -greedy exploration should be kept during the production or testing phase, where no updates will be made to the picking policy. In some problems, it may make sense to keep this exploration feature as the agent may get stuck in the presence of unseen states. This is done successfully in Mnih et al. (2015) while playing Atari games. When solving path problems, non-optimal policies can be affected by cycles in case no randomness is considered. For this reason, we consider that the ϵ parameter is to be maintained when the policy is used in practice.

6.3. Managerial insights

The results shown in the previous sections suggest that the method can learn picking policies to be applied in real retail store environments. Indeed, we can observe the picker learning as he/she achieves higher and higher cumulative rewards. Nonetheless, one may ask whether we need all this work to pick a set of products or if it would be sufficient just to follow more straightforward policies, as is the case of a shortest path policy uniquely based on distance metrics.

The main questions that motivated us to solve this problem remain. Can we improve customer experience? What is the impact on the number of picked orders?

To answer these questions, we measure the performance of four different picking policies regarding business-related indicators, such as the number of orders/products picked and customer encounters.

Q-learning (QL) Policy trained using the devised Q-learning that aims at finding a good compromise for picking orders while avoiding customer encounters.

Shortest Path (SP) Policy based on a shortest path policy (employing a Dijkstra algorithm) aiming at picking the most orders and ignoring customer encounters. Each step is obtained by solving a shortest path problem considering arcs weighted by their length.

Myopic Policy (MP) Policy based on a myopic behavior, which aims at following the nodes with the least customers without getting farther from the target picking position.

Crowded Nodes (CN) Policy that minimizes the number of customer encounters based on a static measure of the average of customers in each node. Each step is obtained by solving a shortest path problem considering arcs weighted by the average number of customers traversing them.

Additionally, for each policy, we considered two types of routing costs to sequence the picking order of the products of an order. Therefore, whenever an online order arrives, the SRP can be solved using a cost matrix considering distances or a crowdedness measure (average number of customers between the origin and destination nodes). These two routing basis are called **Arc Distance** and **Arc Crowdedness**, respectively. This will affect the sequence in which the products of an order are picked.

Table 5 presents the indicators obtained for the four policies using each routing basis considered.

Table 5: Average indicators obtained for 500 episodes of the Shortest Path (SP), Crowded Node (CN), Myopic Policy (MP), and Q-learning (QL) policies.

Routing Basis	Policy	Avg. Rewards	Avg. #Orders	Avg. #Products	Avg. #Encounters
Arc Distance	QL	17615.49	48.86	579.17	1581.91
Arc Distance	SP	17081.50	52.80	628.21	2244.89
Arc Distance	CN	15780.54	43.46	513.50	1139.27
Arc Distance	MP	16195.46	51.54	612.65	2289.23
	Avg.	16668.25	49.17	583.38	1813.83
Arc Crowdedness	QL	17190.52	47.32	562.71	1464.27
Arc Crowdedness	SP	16599.71	50.34	597.57	1928.02
Arc Crowdedness	CN	16864.97	45.24	535.06	1187.86
Arc Crowdedness	MP	15102.30	48.72	579.02	2095.50
	Avg.	16439.38	47.91	568.59	1669.91

Analyzing the case where route sequences are obtained using arc distances, we observe that **SP** and **MP** are the most operationally efficient policies, picking an average of 52.80 and 51.54 orders, respectively. Policies **QL** and **CN** are not so efficient in terms of number of orders picked, picking 48.86 and 43.46 orders, respectively. These policies are clearly focused on improving customer experience, lowering the average number of customer encounters between 30% to 50% compared to policies **SP** and **MP**. Policy **CN** achieves the lowest number of customer encounters, yet it could pick the lowest number of orders among all policies. Policy **QL** drastically reduced the number of customer encounters without heavily compromising the number of orders picked.

Observing the results obtained when route sequences are obtained using the arc crowdedness measure, we observe a similar behavior of the policies, in relative terms, regarding operational efficiency and customer experience. However, the route sequences obtained suffer from a reduction in the average number of orders picked, reducing by 2.56%, from an average of 49.17 orders to 47.91. The number of customer encounters slightly improved, decreasing by 7.99%, from an average of 1813.83 encounters to 1668.91. Therefore, using arc crowdedness as a routing basis helped to find small improvements in customer experience for all policies at the cost of a slight reduction in the number of orders picked.

We observe the most operationally efficient policies are the policies based on following shortest distance paths (**SP** and **MP**). In terms of providing the best customer experience, the **CN** policy achieves the lowest average number of customer encounters. However, these policies are totally focused on one objective only. While the **SP** and **MP** policies cannot avoid customers,

the **CN** policy is not aware that the ultimate objective is to pick orders. The **QL** policy achieves a good compromise in picking a large number of orders and encountering a low average number of customers.

An interesting detail on these results is that the **QL** had to be re-trained when the routing basis was changed from distance to crowdedness. Note that we are dealing with a problem that suffers from the “curse of dimensionality” in the number of states. Given that the route sequences were changed, different pairs of current and target position (state) started appearing more frequently. Since the **QL** policy trained with arc distances had not visited these states sufficiently, the policy had to be trained in an environment where the route sequences considered the arc crowdedness.

The interesting behavior learned by the picker agent can be observed in several origin-destination pairs obtained in the policy. In Figure 9, we present an illustrative example of the paths followed by the **SP**, the **CN**, and the **QL** policies.

Figure 9: Illustrative example of a **SP** path (red), a **CN** path (orange), and a **QL** path (blue).

Although the **SP** policy performs fewer steps (traveling a shorter distance), it visits the most crowded nodes. On the other hand, the **QL** policy follows a longer path, but it tries not to visit crowded nodes, resulting in fewer customer encounters. The **CN** policy performs the longest path as it tries to avoid customers at all cost.

6.4. Robustness of the policies

To demonstrate the flexibility of our approach and the robustness of the learned policies, we present additional computational experiments. In this experiment, we test the learned **QL** policy in different retail environments (considering the baseline environment presented in Section 6.1) by parameterizing our MDP in six different settings:

- **HalfSize**: The arrival rate of the online orders was reduced in half, relatively to the baseline scenario.
- **DoubSize**: The arrival rate of the online orders was doubled relatively to the baseline scenario.
- **HalfOffRate**: The arrival rate of offline customers is cut in half, relatively to the baseline scenario.

- **DoubOffRate**: The arrival rate of offline customers is doubled relatively to the baseline scenario.
- **2OrderBatch**: Picking jobs are composed of two orders that are batched according to their arrival order.
- **CapacityCart**: The picking cart has a capacity that needs to be respected, causing big orders to split.

Table 6 presents the indicators obtained for the six additional settings where the **QL** policy was tested. For each setting, the table shows the (average) number of customers in each episode, the number of orders served, the number of batches created, the number of orders split due to capacity constraints, the number of products picked, and the number of steps (decisions) performed by the picker. Additionally, the table shows four ratios, including the number of steps taken while returning to the depot per order, the number of steps taken to pick a product, the number of customers encountered per product picked, and the reward obtained per product picked.

Table 6: Average indicators obtained for 500 episodes of the Q-learning (QL) policy for each additional setting.

Setting	Avg. #Cust.	Avg. #Orders	Avg. #Batches	Avg. #Splits	Avg. #Products	Avg. #Steps	Avg. Steps To Depot Per Order	Avg. Steps Per Prod.	Avg. Encounters Per Prod.	Avg. Rewards Per Prod.
Baseline	145.04	47.02	47.02	0.00	559.02	5921.98	11.91	10.59	2.86	29.03
HalfSize	145.45	64.68	64.68	0.00	386.91	6528.43	16.00	16.87	4.07	22.49
DoubSize	144.45	31.66	31.66	0.00	760.02	5151.32	8.30	6.78	2.08	34.23
HalfOffRate	72.59	47.45	47.45	0.00	564.08	5888.79	11.85	10.44	1.42	38.56
DoubOffRate	290.14	47.75	47.75	0.00	569.02	5889.37	11.82	10.35	5.59	11.42
2OrderBatch	145.01	64.79	32.40	0.00	741.73	5060.05	3.53	6.82	2.05	34.39
CapacityCart	145.37	39.94	39.94	1.71	529.04	6405.12	32.73	12.11	2.89	26.20

We observe relatively intuitive results regarding the direction of the impact introduced in each indicator.

When the number of products per online order is reduced, as in the **HalfSize** setting, the picker is able to pick more orders (64.68), but since the product positions may be more sparse across the store, he/she needs more steps to pick a product (16.68). Additionally, to pick more products, he/she will do more steps towards the depot (16.00) and encounter more offline customers (4.07). An opposite behavior is observed in the **DoubSize** setting.

When the rate of offline customer arrivals is reduced, as in the **HalfOffRate** setting, the number of orders picked remains unchanged, but the number of customers in the store is cut in half (72.59). This also reduces customer encounters per product picked (1.42). This is also the setting that achieves more rewards per product picked (38.56). An opposite behavior is observed in the **DoubOffRate** setting.

In the **2OrderBatch** setting, where batches of two orders are created, the picker is able to pick more products (741.73) and needs fewer steps to pick a product (6.82). He/she is also able to reduce the number of encounters per product (2.05) and spends fewer steps returning to the depot (3.53).

Finally, when the picker pulls a capacitated cart, as in the **CapacityCart** setting, some orders must be split, and additional trips to the preparation zone are necessary. We observe that the number of steps taken toward the preparation zone increases substantially (32.73). Interestingly, the number of steps per product suffers a slight increase (12.11), but the number of customer encounters per product remains unchanged (2.89).

These results suggest that the learned policies are flexible and applicable to various retail environments. Furthermore, they are robust and maintain an expected behavior.

7. Conclusion

This paper proposes a new problem in omnichannel retail, the diPRP, and solves it through a reinforcement learning approach. This problem has gained particular relevance due to the substantial increase in e-commerce shopping that occurred after the pandemic context of 2020. Several retailers deployed new online shopping services, such as BOPS and SFS, which resorted to in-store picking operations performed in existing physical retail stores. Besides operational efficiency, several retailers adapted their picking policies to focus on novel customer-oriented metrics, such as the number of customers encountered during a picking route. Note that these customers are typically disturbed by the picker carts parked in the aisles. These new picking operations will not be temporary. They will prevail as an essential fulfillment method among omnichannel retail players. We tackled the real-world case of a retailer that aimed at having its in-store pickers seeking products while hiding from customers. This strategy came up as a solution to reduce the number of customer encounters, an essential component of the customer shopping experience nowadays.

Our solution approach encompasses several techniques, integrating the fields of mathematical programming, simulation, and machine learning, to obtain an in-store picking policy that is competitive in terms of the number of picked products while minimizing the number of customer encounters. Our study provides evidence that reinforcement learning can be an essential method for effectively solving new management problems. The devised solution approach trains picker agents to perform shopping paths that reduce the disturbance of in-store customers during their shopping experience. Computational experiments performed both on synthetic instances and a real-world instance from a large European retailer show that the picker agents can learn efficient picking policies in a reasonable number of episodes. An vital characteristic inherent to our approach is the low computational power demanded and the very short computational time required to obtain a decision.

7.1. Managerial implications

Based on the real-world case study, we provide interesting numeric results and solution visualizations to support a few managerial insights. As expected, the shopping sequences followed by the customers often result in crowded store areas. Due to the dynamic and unpredictable movement in-store, these crowded store areas are difficult to predict. However, we observe that the devised picking policies avoid these areas to reduce the number of customer encounters. This is not the behavior of the shortest path-based policies, which, logically, can pick a few more products, but nearly double the number of customers disturbed in our simulations. Our approach, based on reinforcement learning, allows better control over the trade-off between operational efficiency and customer experience. Such a result may empower retailers to pursue their omnichannel fulfillment strategy further.

The learned policies were further tested in six different settings, which were obtained by varying important retail parameters, such as the size of each order, the arrival rate of the offline customers, the size of the order batches, and the capacity of the picker cart. Interesting insights were revealed. For instance, creating batches of two orders increased the number of products picked and reduced the average number of customers encountered per product picked. Another interesting insight was obtained when a capacitated cart was considered, as splitting orders largely increased the number of steps taken by the picker while returning to the order preparation zone. Note that rather than providing surprising results, these tests reveal that

both the approach and the learned policies are applicable to a considerable number of retail settings.

7.2. Limitations and future work

Naturally, this work has some limitations that should be tackled in future works regarding in-store picking operations in omnichannel retail.

Offline customer arrival rate Our MDP assumes that offline customer arrivals follow a homogeneous Poisson process. However, we know from retail practice and retail literature that customer demand is often time-dependent. This means there are stores with a peak in the morning, evening, or both. This limitation could be addressed in two different ways: (1) Modelling different parts of the day with a different homogeneous Poisson process and learning a different policy for each of them; (2) Modelling a non-homogeneous Poisson process and considering the time dimension in the picking policy.

Limited demand context This work applies to cases where the retailer has an extensive store network that needs to serve a limited amount of online orders. Although this is the case for many omnichannel retailers, in an omnichannel retail setting with a large number of online orders, it may be necessary to consider warehouse-based models or hybrid models which can serve online orders either from a warehouse or from a store.

Policy generalization The policies we are extracting need to be trained on the graph of the specific store in which they will be used. We plan to explore the possibility of extracting generic policies and learning from more complex features (richer state variables).

Picker and cart decoupling In this particular problem, the picker cart has the most significant responsibility for disturbing customers. Therefore, to clearly capture the disturbance caused by in-store picking with carts, the MDP would need to consider picker and cart decoupling. Furthermore, the picking policy would need to be more complex, indicating where to leave the cart in each picker move.

Evaluating customer satisfaction Although the considered retailer has a significant interest in implementing the proposed approach, we could not measure the real impact of reducing customer encounters on the satisfaction of the customers. This is a limitation we aim to address when our approach is deployed.

Many developments can be further introduced in this problem. For instance, developing collaborative picking policies to coordinate picking teams in this problem would be an interesting exercise, particularly if the customer perception regarding the number of picker encounters can be assessed. Additionally, improvements to the simulation environment can be introduced to consider, for example, slowdowns experienced in crowded aisles. Furthermore, exploring richer state variables may improve the quality of the picking policies. For instance, the number of customers encountered in each aisle can further influence the decision of the picker in an online fashion (probably, the state space would suffer from the so-called “curse of dimensionality” more severely in this case). Lastly, we would like to stress that there are multiple applications for the approach proposed in this paper. The future reserves the automation of several activities, such as robots for cleaning public spaces, robots for picking products at warehouses and stores, and autonomous vehicles. These technologies will likely be placed in narrow spaces shared with humans. Since these automations are typically not pleasant to the eye, our approach is an interesting alternative for the future of omnichannel retail.

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Appendix A. Notation

MIP (Section 4.1.1)

Indices

- i, j Picking position
- o Online order

Sets

- \mathcal{G} Graph composed of sets $(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$
- \mathcal{V} Set of vertices
- \mathcal{E} Set of arcs
- \mathcal{L}_o Set of picking positions of online order o

Parameters

- w_{ij} Travelled distance to traverse arc (i, j)

Decision Variables

- x_{ij} Equal to one if arc (i, j) is traversed, zero otherwise

MDP (Section 3)

Indices

- k Decision epoch
- c Offline customer
- o Online order

Sets

- T Set of time periods
- \mathcal{S} Set of states
- \mathcal{A} Set of actions
- R Reward function
- P Transition probabilities (unknown)
- \mathcal{C} Set of offline customer shopping paths
- \mathcal{O} Set of shopping lists (online orders)

State variables

- s_0 Initial state
- s_k State associated with decision epoch k
- a_k Action chosen at decision epoch k
- n_k Current location of the picker at decision epoch k
- z_k Target location of the picker at decision epoch k
- t_k Time at decision epoch k
- r_k Reward associated with decision epoch k
- ω Exogenous information revealed at decision epoch k
- \mathcal{L}_o Shopping list of online customer o
- θ_o Picking sequence of online order o
- θ_c Picking sequence followed by offline customer c
- λ^{Online} Online order arrival rate
- λ^{Store} Offline customer arrival rate
- $speed^{Customer}$ Customer's walking speed
- $service_time^{Customer}$ Time spent by a customer for picking a product
- $speed^{Picker}$ Picker walking speed
- $service_time^{Picker}$ Time spent by the picker for picking a product
- $|\mathcal{C}|$ Maximum number of offline customers allowed in the store
- m Maximum number of physical customers allowed in a location node

Q-Learning (Section 4.2)

- $\pi(s)$ Policy
 - $V_{\pi(s)}(s)$ Value function
 - γ Discount rate
 - ϵ Exploration rate
 - α Learning rate
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